

Influence of Music Therapy on Cardiorespiratory Parameters and Stress Levels in Mechanically Ventilated Patients**Mohit Mishra¹, Rachna Parashar², Saurabh Saigal³, Waqas Alauddin⁴, Rajay Bharshankar⁵, Avinash Thakare⁶, Shashwat Arora⁷**¹Assistant Professor, Department of Physiology, Naraina Medical College and Research Centre, Kanpur, Uttar Pradesh, IND²Associate Professor, Department of Physiology, All India Institute of Medical Sciences, Bhopal, IND³Professor, Department of Anesthesiology, All India Institute of Medical Sciences, Bhopal, IND⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Physiology, Naraina Medical College and Research Centre, Kanpur, IND⁵Professor, Department of Physiology, All India Institute of Medical Sciences, Bhopal, IND⁶Associate Professor, Department of Physiology, All India Institute of Medical Sciences, Bhopal, IND⁷Second year MBBS student, Naraina Medical College & Research Centre, Kanpur, IND

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Abstract:**Background:** An innovative approach for treating patients in intensive care units on mechanical ventilation is music therapy. Its effectiveness in lowering stress and improving both physical and mental health has not been thoroughly studied, despite its historical use in healing. The present study delves deeper into the effects of music therapy on critically ill patients in India, emphasizing how it can alleviate financial burden, enhance haemodynamics, and lessen anxiety and discomfort.**Objective:** The study's objective is to evaluate how music therapy affects mechanically ventilated patients' cardiorespiratory parameters and stress levels.**Methods:** Thirty patients on mechanical ventilation participated in the interventional study, both males and females with age range of 18 to 65 years, which was conducted at AIIMS in Bhopal, India. Cardiorespiratory parameters such as HR - heart rate, RR- respiratory rate, SPO2- oxygen saturation, SBP - systolic blood pressure, DBP- diastolic blood pressure, TV- tidal volume, PEEP positive end-respiratory pressure, PaO2- partial pressure of oxygen in arterial blood, PaO2/FiO2- pressure of oxygen in arterial blood to the fraction of inspired oxygen concentration, PP- positive pressure, PIP -peak inspiratory pressure, and FiO2%- fraction of inspired oxygen were measured both before and after music therapy. During these patients' music therapy sessions, low-pitched instrumental music for relaxation and meditation was played. Blood samples were taken in order to determine the serum cortisol and IL-1 levels. Data was assembled and entered using Microsoft Excel, and it was analysed using licensed statistical software, SPSS version 21.0 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY)**Results:** In the intervention group, HR ($p = 0.001$), BP systolic ($p = 0.001$), BP diastolic ($p < 0.0001$), PIP (< 0.0001), PP ($p = 0.004$), PEEP ($p < 0.0001$), RR ($p = 0.016$), and PaO2/FiO2 ($p = 0.002$), showed a significant decrease as compared to the baseline pre-music therapy group. TV ($p = 0.039$) FiO2 ($p < 0.0001$) and SPO2 ($p < 0.001$), showed significant increase in the post-music therapy intervention group as compared to the baseline pre-music therapy group. Serum cortisol showed a significant decrease from in the post-music therapy intervention group ($p < 0.0001$), whereas IL-1 was also decreased but the difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.133$)**Conclusion:** This study reveals that music therapy for mechanically ventilated patients significantly improves cardiovascular and stress levels with improvements in respiratory parameters. Thus, further research is needed to explore more of the effects on respiratory parameters. This can be a promising supportive treatment in the future, further helping to decrease their weaning time on mechanical ventilation.**Keywords:** cardiorespiratory parameters, stress levels, medical intensive care unit (MICU), music therapy, mechanical ventilation.

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Introduction

Music therapy is an innovative, novel approach with several potential benefits for patients in the intensive care unit (ICU) who are on mechanical ventilation. [1] As an example of the significance of music in human growth and medicine, the American Music Therapy Association (AMTA) describes music therapy as the clinical and evidence-based use of musical treatments to accomplish individualised goals within a therapeutic partnership. [2] In music therapy, patients can choose the music they want to hear, while medical professionals use headphones to passively listen to pre-recorded music for listening treatments. [3] Despite music's historical usage in healing, its efficacy in lowering stress and enhancing physical and mental health has not been fully investigated by researchers. Dr. Kane documented in 1914 how phonograph treatment improved anaesthetic tolerance and decreased anxiety in his patients. [4] In 1918, Hyde and Scalapino's EKG-based experiment showed that upbeat music elevates blood pressure and pulse rate, whereas minor tones decrease both. After the war, musicians performed for returning soldiers, popularising music therapy for critically ill patients. [5] Patients in intensive care units, especially those on mechanical breathing, frequently struggle with stress and worry. Through relaxation, music medicine can assist with these problems. [6] Patients in intensive care units experience stress due to the continuous medical tests, operations, and monitoring. High noise levels that are present at the same time, such as alarm noises, can lead to confusion, weariness, tension, and worry. [7] The goal of MV is to enhance gas exchange and breathing effectiveness without reinjuring the lungs or respiratory muscles. Calm music is defined as having a leisurely pace, low pitch, low volume, and melodic rhythms that are mostly played by wind instruments. [8,9] Because it lowers stress and cortisol levels, music medicine is used in clinical practice to stabilise mood before invasive procedures and in intensive care units. Because of their loudness and rhyme scheme, heavy metal and techno music are regarded as hazardous or ineffectual in the field of intensive care medicine. Having quiet tones and minimal rhythms makes classical music introspective, patient, and helpful. [10,11]. However, there is a dearth of research on music medicine's impact on patients on mechanical ventilation in India. The aim of this study is to assess the impact of music therapy on critically ill patients in the intensive care unit who are on mechanical ventilation. Specifically, the study will look at how music therapy may lessen financial strain, enhance haemodynamics, and lessen discomfort and stress levels.

Materials and Methods

This pre- and post-interventional research was conducted after ethical clearance. The institutional ethics committee granted permission to carry out the research from June 2021 to December 2022 at the critical care unit of the All India Institute of Medical Sciences (AIIMS) in Bhopal, India with ethical approval number IHECPGRMD028. A written consent from patients was obtained. This study was performed on 30 patients who were on mechanical ventilation. Baseline data on cardiorespiratory parameters, such as blood pressure, heart rate, respiration rate, tidal volume, and saturated oxygen (spo₂), were taken both before and after the first music session. [3] The total number of sedatives and analgesics taken by the group during the duration of the investigation was calculated. The study's patients, who were brought to the intensive care unit (ICU) after receiving mechanical breathing for the preceding 48 hours, varied in age range from 18 to 65 years, both males and females were included in the study. Apart from these, those patients receiving small doses of inotropes or vasopressors both maintained stable haemodynamics were also included. The experimental group was exposed to thirty minutes of daily, spaced eight hours apart, pre-recorded, low-pitched, low-volume instrumental music designed for meditation and relaxation was given. This was done for a total of seventy-two hours. [3] Patients who fulfill the following above criteria were included in the study, classified as American Society of Anesthesiologists (ASA) grade 1 or 2, and be a male or female participant [12]. Patients' physiological status was evaluated and surgical risk was forecasted using the ASA physical status classification system. Patients with an ASA physical status of three or above, people who declined to participate in the study, people with psychological disorders, and people on antidepressant or anxiety medication were among the exclusion criteria. Music therapy was first provided at 8 a.m., then repeated every 8 hours. Regardless of age or gender, patients in the intensive care unit (ICU) who are admitted and have been on mechanical breathing for the last 48 hours satisfy the inclusion criteria. Following an overnight fast, blood samples were drawn, serum cortisol levels and IL-1 were measured, the enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) was used to evaluate the blood levels of IL-1 in the patients. The test quantifies the degree to which matched pairs of antibodies bind to the target. [13]

Statistical analysis

Data was assembled and entered using Microsoft Excel, and it was analysed using licensed statistical software, SPSS version 21.0 (IBM Corp., Armonk,

NY). To display the data, mean and standard deviation (SD) were employed. The statistical significance of the differences between the pre- and post-intervention assessments was ascertained using the paired Student t-test, also known as a non-parametric test. The threshold of significance for a p-value was set at less than or equal to 0.05.

Results

Out of 30 patients, 21 were males and 9 were females, and the mean age of the patients were 45.50 ± 15.51 years and the age range was between 18 to 65 years who underwent music therapy.

We examined pre- and post-music therapy data, measuring cardio-respiratory parameters such as heart rate (HR), respiratory rate (RR), oxygen saturation (SPO₂), systolic blood pressure (SBP), diastolic blood pressure (DBP), tidal volume (TV),

positive end-respiratory pressure (PEEP), partial pressure of oxygen in arterial blood (PaO₂), partial pressure of oxygen in arterial blood to the fraction of inspired oxygen concentration (PaO₂/FiO₂), positive pressure (PP), peak inspiratory pressure (PIP), and fraction of inspired oxygen (FiO₂%).

Cardiorespiratory parameters in mechanically ventilated patients: As depicted in table 1, In the intervention group, HR ($p = 0.001^*$), BP systolic ($p = 0.001^*$), BP diastolic ($p < 0.0001^*$), PaO₂/FiO₂ ($p = 0.002^*$), PIP ($p < 0.0001^*$), PP ($p = 0.004^*$), PEEP ($p < 0.0001^*$) and RR ($p = 0.016^*$), showed a significant decrease as compared to the baseline pre-music therapy group. Whereas TV ($p = 0.039^*$), and FiO₂ ($p < 0.0001^*$) showed significant increase in the post-music therapy intervention group as compared to the baseline pre-music therapy group.

Table 1: Comparison of baseline and post music therapy parameters in mechanically ventilated patients

	Baseline parameters (Mean \pm SD)	Post-therapy parameters (Mean \pm SD)	P-value
HR (bpm)	89.03 \pm 15.66	86.67 \pm 15.31	0.0001*
SBP (mmHg)	138.53 \pm 19.85	134.67 \pm 19.85	0.0001*
DBP (mmHg)	94.20 \pm 15.04	90.47 \pm 15.08	0.0001*
PaO ₂ /FiO ₂	199.17 \pm 67.98	193.00 \pm 62.39	0.002*
RR(bpm)	23.13 \pm 3.59	22.33 \pm 4.24	0.016*
TV (ml)	585.00 \pm 49.39	601.67 \pm 46.39	0.039*
PIP	26.37 \pm 6.72	24.93 \pm 7.36	0.0001*
PP	34.13 \pm 4.26	32.27 \pm 4.49	0.004*
PEEP	9.53 \pm 3.22	8.40 \pm 3.31	0.0001*
FiO ₂ (%)	0.47 \pm 0.11	0.54 \pm 0.09	0.0001*
SPO ₂ (%)	92.13	92.97	0.001*

*p-value less than 0.05 is significant, SD- standard deviation, bpm- beats per minute

HR - heart rate, RR- respiratory rate, SPO₂- oxygen saturation, SBP - systolic blood pressure, DBP- diastolic blood pressure, TV- tidal volume, PEEP- positive end-respiratory pressure, PaO₂- partial pressure of oxygen in arterial blood, PaO₂/FiO₂- pressure of oxygen in arterial blood to the fraction of inspired oxygen concentration, PP- positive pressure, PIP -peak inspiratory pressure, and FiO₂%- fraction of inspired oxygen

Stress parameters in mechanically ventilated patients: As seen in table 2, Serum cortisol levels

and IL-1 at baseline and after therapy were compared.

Serum cortisol showed a significant decrease from 21.54 ± 5.57 mcg/dl to 18.75 ± 5.98 mcg/dl in the post-music therapy intervention group ($p < 0.0001^*$).

IL-1 was decreased in the post-music therapy intervention group as compared to the baseline, but the difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.133$).

Table 2: Comparison of baseline and post music therapy serum cortisol and inflammatory marker in mechanically ventilated patients

	Baseline parameters (Mean \pm SD)	Post-therapy parameters (Mean \pm SD)	P-value
Serum-Cortisol (mcg/dl)	21.54 \pm 5.57	18.75 \pm 5.98	0.0001*
IL-1	135.91 \pm 141.02	79.80 \pm 89.18	0.133

*p-value < 0.05 Significant, SD- standard deviation, IL- Interleukin

Discussion

The interventional group's physiological measures differ considerably from the control groups,

indicating the effectiveness of music therapy. Following the intervention, the post-music medicine measures revealed a significant decrease in heart rate, systolic and diastolic blood pressure,

respiratory rate, PaO₂/FiO₂, PIP, PP, PEEP and significant increase in TV and FiO₂.

Our results yielded similar findings of Golino et al., who looked at how an active music therapy intervention affected patients in critical care units. [14] Similar to our study, according to Bradt and Dileo et al.'s findings, Patients receiving mechanical ventilation who consistently listen to music see a reduction in their systolic blood pressure and respiratory rate, leading to a relaxing reaction. [15] They found reduced heart rate and hormone levels. [15]

A study reveals that music, as a non-pharmacological intervention, significantly impacts the physiological, psychological, and social responses of mechanically ventilated patients. [16] It decreases heart rate, blood pressure, breathing, pain intensity, anxiety levels, sleep disturbances, delirium occurrence, and improves cognitive function which may be related to psychophysiological changes causing a decrease in the sympathetic nervous system. [16]

We also found that Serum cortisol levels and IL-1 were decreased after music therapy, former been significantly decreased, which had detrimental psychological impacts over time. It has been found that there is a relationship between the degree of surgical trauma and cortisol concentration, and that cortisol is a major stress response signal. [17] In patients, the Chlan et al. study looked at cortisol, or inflammatory blood levels, as a possible sign of stress-related anxiety. [18]

The study's findings were somewhat inconsistent due to patient comorbidities, acute renal failure or insufficiency, or drugs that may alter cortisol levels. This demonstrated that cortisol levels and music treatments as a means of lowering overall stress were not correlated in the study. [18] The effectiveness of the intervention is influenced by the choice of music and Music therapy is highly effective in reducing anxiety, pain, and agitation in confused patients. [16]

Another study by Hunter et al. found that active music therapy has been shown to be an effective way to alleviate anxiety during the weaning off of mechanical breathing. [19] They provided in-person sessions, adjusting the music's volume and speed in accordance with the patient's breathing and pulse rate. [19] As a result, significant changes in breathing and heart rates occurred, and anxiety levels decreased. [19] Our results show the same thing.

According to a recent study, there was a noticeable drop in anxiety, which allowed the patient on ventilator care to listen to music whenever they wanted. [20] Stress is a common occurrence for patients in critical care units, particularly for those

on mechanical ventilation. [20] The patient's general health and capacity to recover may be negatively impacted by anxiety. The negative effects could prolong the healing and weaning process. [20] Patients who are critically ill usually react well to music therapy, which is a widely used stress reduction technique in all branches of medicine. It can reduce the stress response, cause a general relaxation response, and lessen anxiety during mechanical breathing without the need for medicine. [5] Thus, the results of this study suggest that the parameters associated with cardiorespiratory and ventilators (HR, RR, oxygen saturation, blood pressure, tidal volume, PEEP, PIP, PP, FiO₂/PaO₂, FiO₂%) are strongly impacted by frequent music therapy. This study shows that music therapy improves cardiovascular parameters by significantly lowering heart rate and systolic and diastolic blood pressure in patients on mechanical ventilation. Music therapy also significant decrease in respiratory rate, PaO₂/FiO₂, PIP, PP, PEEP and significant increase in TV and FiO₂, spo₂ in patients on mechanical ventilation, suggesting improvement respiratory parameters. More research is needed to fully explore these mechanisms. Thus, it also reduces anxiety and shortens hospital stays by helping patients wean off artificial ventilation earlier.

The study has limitations due to its methodological quality and smaller sample size. Thus, a larger sample size study needs to be performed in the future for in-depth knowledge. There is a lack of standardised tools for measuring the effect of music therapy on patients' well-being, as well as the intervention used. As our study is primarily comprised of males, we recommend a study that is exclusively performed on females. It also differs from American Music Therapy Association recommendations, with some studies focusing on music therapy and others focusing on patient-directed music therapy.

Conclusions

This study reveals that music therapy in mechanically ventilated patient's significant decrease in heart rate, systolic and diastolic blood pressure, respiratory rate, PaO₂/FiO₂, PIP, PP, PEEP and significant increase in TV and FiO₂ pointing towards improvement of respiratory parameters, which needs further studies to delve deeper to explore various mechanisms. Additionally, music therapy significantly lowers serum cortisol. These effects of music therapy can be promising as a supportive therapy in the future, helping to decrease their weaning time on mechanical ventilation.

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